

Learning Without Borders: The Future of MOOCs in Europe

Annechien Helsdingen¹ and Ulrike Wild²

¹ École Polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne, 1015 CH, Lausanne, Switzerland

² Wageningen University and Research, 6708PB Wageningen, The Netherlands

annechien.helsdingen@epfl.ch

Keywords: MOOC strategy, MOOC infrastructure, course platform, course exchange, inter-institutional collaboration.

1 Background

More than a decade after the emergence of the first MOOC platforms, both MOOCs and their hosting platforms continue to evolve and expand. Alongside global players like Coursera, FutureLearn, and edX, numerous national initiatives have been launched in various countries over the past ten years. Nevertheless, many European institutions still primarily deliver their courses through US-based platforms.

This workshop aims to explore MOOC strategies, international partnerships, and infrastructure needs within European Higher Education institutions, as well as organisations providing professional and lifelong learning opportunities. It also marks the official launch of **Open Learnity** — an Open edX platform driven by the Swiss MOOC (SMS) Association. Open Learnity welcomes Higher Education institutions and Non-Governmental Organisations from across Europe, operating as a co-owned platform governed collaboratively by its member organisations.

Goals

To explore the current state, future potential, and strategic choices surrounding MOOCs and open online education in European higher education. Together, we want to reflect on institutional strategies, use cases, infrastructure needs, and the potential for European collaboration — without presuming a single dominant model.

2 Preliminary Programme

09:30	Welcome and introduction <i>Framing the purpose, aims, and open, exploratory nature of the workshop.</i>
-------	---

09:40	European Perspective of Open Learnity: Mission, Organisation and Governance.
09:55	Current Trends in MOOCs and Open Online Education in Europe <i>Short presentation providing context, trends, examples of diverse institutional strategies and dilemmas.</i>
10:30	Breakout Round 1: What Are We Doing Now? <i>In groups, participants discuss current MOOC use cases, internal and external infrastructure, and institutional strategies.</i>
10:50	Plenary discussion
11:15	Coffee break
11:30	Breakout Round 2: Future Opportunities and Dilemmas <i>Participants reflect on future opportunities, challenges, and European collaboration possibilities. Key questions:</i> - <i>Is 'MOOC' still the right term?</i> - <i>Need for national or European platforms?</i> - <i>Policies on online assessment and credit exchange?</i> - <i>Technical and infrastructural consequences?</i> - <i>MOOC types for diverse audiences?</i>
11:50	Plenary Reflection: Towards Shared Perspectives
12:05	Open Discussion: What Could or Should We Do Together? <i>Collective brainstorm on possible next steps, collaborations, and priorities for European cooperation.</i>
12:30	Closing

Why this workshop is relevant for EMOOCs 2025

Open online education is evolving rapidly, and European universities are navigating a landscape of new opportunities and challenges. From professional education to lifelong learning, from MOOCs as books to MOOCs as prerequisites for on-campus programs — the range of applications is expanding.

To support these activities, it's essential to have a platform that is open, reliable, and accessible to students from all participating universities — using authentication systems compatible with their home institutions. The Open Learnity platform provides this functionality. Managed by an Association of member universities, it offers a shared, neutral, and co-owned infrastructure for course exchange and collaborative online teaching.

3 Why Join the workshop?

We warmly invite colleagues from all MOOC providers and platforms who are eager to look ahead and contribute to shaping a distinctive European MOOC model. This workshop offers a space to share experiences, reflect on existing strategies, and collectively explore new directions for MOOCs and open online education in Europe.

Together, we will examine practical use cases, infrastructure needs, policy challenges, and opportunities for collaboration both nationally and across Europe. The workshop is designed as an open, exploratory forum — not grounded in predetermined solutions, but focused on learning from one another and capturing the diversity of perspectives within our community.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.